

Noether's Theorem and Claius' Heat Term

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Noether's theorem demonstrates a relation between a symmetry in the Lagrangian and a conserved quantity. As shown in (1), $d/dt \partial L / \partial \dot{q} = \partial L / \partial q$. If $\partial L / \partial q = 0$, then $d/dt \partial L / \partial \dot{q} = \text{momentum} = \text{constant}$. In other words, the absence of a potential $V(x)$ (as $L=T-V$ usually in nonrelativistic mechanics) means momentum is conserved because there is invariance in space. We argue that $V(x)$ specifically implies a constraint in space. We suggest that a constraint breaks symmetry and try to use this view with Noether's theorem in what follows.

In (2), it is argued that one may consider the First Law of Thermodynamics in terms of d/dt Hamiltonian where Hamiltonian $= \dot{q} \partial L / \partial \dot{q} - L$. Specifically, $L(q, \dot{q}, b)$ where b is called a parameter which is ultimately linked with thermodynamic work. We suggest then that it may be volume as an example. A Lagrangian formalism is introduced in (2) and $dE/dt = d\text{Hamiltonian}/dt$ associated with the first law of thermodynamics. A term linked to db/dt is argued to represent δ Work and a d Noether conserved quantity is called δ heat.

We argue here that it seems difficult to map such a Lagrangian directly to an ideal gas in the form in which it appears. In particular, if b is Volume, then $H=\text{energy}$ is not a function of volume directly as shown in (2), but a change in volume changes imparts extra energy to particles in the gas through collisions. We do, however, try to argue that there may be a link with Noether's theorem in the following way.

In the first paragraph, we suggested that a spatial constraint may be linked with spatial symmetry breaking. For an ideal gas, one has many particles and the total energy is the sum of their kinetic energies (nonrelativistically). At the same time, an ideal gas implies a physical constraint to give it a volume. One may change the energy of particles by specific work on the particles in a manner not linked to any physical constraint, or one may impart energy by changing the physical constraint. The physical constraint suggests a symmetry breaking, while the non-symmetry breaking hits linked with heat might be construed to be similar to a symmetry based constant in Noether's theorem. In particular, $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ which means a collision happens due to work. In the ideal gas, we map this to a moving wall. If $dV/dx=0$, the $p = \text{constant}$. This is a Noether constant. Then dp means that the Noether constant changes even though there is no spatial symmetry breaking. A change in p means a change in $pp/2m$, so δ heat should be linked to such a notion.

We, however, do not use any kind of Lagrangian and so this association is based on a global constraint (volume) used to impart energy versus a non-constraint approach of applying energy. In particular, we try to think in terms of the classical mechanics of a single particle in the gas.

Noether's Theorem

According to (1), Noether's theorem implies that there is a conserved quantity linked with a symmetry in a Lagrangian. Specifically:

$$d/dt \partial L / \partial \dot{q} = \partial L / \partial q \quad ((1))$$

If $dL/dq=0$, this implies a symmetry because L is independent of q . Then:

$$dL / d \dot{q} = \text{constant} = \text{momentum} \quad ((2))$$

Often nonrelativistically one has, $L = T - V$, where T is kinetic energy (nonrelativistic case) and $V(x)$, potential energy. For $dL/dq \text{ partial} = 0$, $dV/dx \text{ partial} = 0$. In other words, there is a constant potential or no specific constraint on a particle at x . The constraint, $-dV/dx$, is of the form of a force which delivers an impulse hit to a particle. Thus, for a conserved quantity to exist, we suggest that there is no constraining force in x .

We suggest that such a view could be mapped to an ideal gas. In particular, a gas contains a very specific spatial constraint in x , namely the presence of a wall. If this wall moves, it may impart energy to particles in the gas, but the presence of the wall means that it is a symmetry-breaking term which imparts energy. If there is no such symmetry-breaking term (and no change of it) which imparts energy, one may still impart energy in a non-spatial symmetry-breaking manner by having photons deliver energy to the particles in the gas. We suggest that this is why one might associate heat with a non-symmetry breaking term in (2). We try to clarify these ideas by describing the approach of (2).

Approach of (2) Linking Heat in the First Law of Thermodynamics to a Change in a Conserved Quantity in Noether's Theorem

Noether's theorem is based on Lagrangian formalism. In (2), a Hamiltonian is written a priori as:

$$E(q, \dot{q}, b) = \text{Hamiltonian}(q, \dot{q}, b) = \dot{q} dL/d\dot{q} \text{ partial} - L \quad ((3))$$

Here b is called a parameter and q a generalized co-ordinate. A main idea of (2) is to write:

$$dE/dt = -\dot{q} \{ d/dt dL/d\dot{q} \text{ partial} - dL/dq \text{ partial} \} - d/db \text{ partial} (dL/d \dot{q} \text{ partial} \dot{q}) \quad db/dt \quad ((4))$$

The term in $\{ \}$ is said to represent delta heat and the second term, delta work, as some general parameter b is changed. We try to link ((4)) with an ideal gas, but have difficulties because although b seems to clearly be V , volume, it is not clear what q and \dot{q} represent. In other words, Noether's theorem requires Lagrangian formalism and so a kind of Lagrangian is presented in ((3)) (actually a Hamiltonian based on a Lagrangian).

(2) goes on to describe the term ins $\{ \}$ as dN where N is a conserved Noether quantity, but with dN meaning that it is changing. We refer to (2) for details which are based explicitly on the choice of ((3)). In other words, all conclusions follow from the use of ((3)).

Changing Constraints as Symmetry-Breaking Terms of Noether's Theorem

We suggest examining this problem in terms of constraints as the symmetry-breaking pieces of Noether's theorem. In particular, for a single particle in classical mechanics:

$$d/dt \frac{dL}{dq} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial q} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, it is $\frac{\partial L}{\partial q}$ which breaks symmetry and prevents the conservation of $\frac{dL}{dq}$ = momentum. $\frac{\partial L}{\partial q}$, however, is traditionally:

$$-\frac{\partial V}{\partial q} \text{ where } V(q) \text{ is a potential } ((6))$$

It is the potential which breaks spatial symmetry by imparting a different force at different q points. This potential is thus a kind of constraint directly linked with space which does work.

To apply this concept to an ideal gas, we suggest that a spatial constraint which breaks spatial symmetry is the wall of the container holding the gas. In general, this wall is linked with elastic scattering of particles in the gas, but if the wall moves, i.e. db/dt , then it may impart energy to the particles. This is work performed linked to $\frac{\partial L}{\partial q} dq$, which means that p (momentum) of a single particle is not conserved if it strikes the wall.

There exists, however, a way to change energy by introducing interactions not associated with a symmetry breaking spatial constraint. In particular, an ideal gas may absorb photons which impart energy to the particles in a non-spatial symmetry breaking manner. This then immediately leads to two terms:

$$d\text{Energy} = \Delta \text{heat} - \Delta \text{Work} \quad ((7))$$

Δheat is linked with no spatial symmetry breaking (like a conserved quantity in Noether's theorem) and ΔWork , with spatial symmetry breaking and a spatial constraint. Δheat , however, means heat is changing (i.e. energy is being added due to the non-breaking of a spatial symmetry or constraint). One might think of Δheat as being related to dp , i.e. momentum changes of single particles without any change in the volume. One may then call momentum the Noether conserved quantity if $\frac{\partial L}{\partial q} = 0$.

In (2), matters are a little different, but ΔWork is associated directly with symmetry breaking through db/dt and heat, with a conserved quantity.

To say that p is conserved for each particle, then dp means that $p^2/2m$ changes for the various particles and so too does energy.

We thus suggest that the link between the First Law of Thermodynamics and Noether's theorem, i.e. symmetry versus symmetry breaking terms and their changes is due to the volume constraint of a gas breaking spatial symmetry. This breaking of symmetry can lead to dp/dt , i.e. change the energy of the gas and is called work. A non-spatial symmetry breaking interaction (with photons), however, can change energy without breaking symmetry. Noether's theorem suggests that the quantity which is conserved appears if one sets symmetry breaking to zero. This means $\frac{\partial L}{\partial q} = 0$ and p is conserved, so if energy is changed without changing b

(Volume), it should be through changing p in (2) in another manner. Thus, dN Noether conserved quantity is linked with d heat, we argue in such a manner (i.e. examining a single particle).

Conclusion

Noether's theorem explicitly makes use of Lagrangian formalism, so to apply it to the First Law of Thermodynamics, a Lagrangian must be introduced as is done in (2). We find it difficult, however, to map this Lagrangian and corresponding Hamiltonian (q, \dot{q}, b) to an ideal gas, except for the association of b with Volume. (2) suggests that a change in volume (b) is associated with thermodynamic work. Such work is due to changing a spatial constraint which applies to the gas, namely moving a wall. We associate this with the term, dL/dq partial, which means that p =momentum must change from Lagrange theory. In other words, we associate spatial symmetry breaking, which is usually linked with $V(x)$, a potential in space, to the moving wall of a gas which is also a constraint breaking spatial symmetry and can impart energy.

From Lagrangian theory, if such a spatial symmetry breaking does not exist, $d/dt p = 0$ and p is a conserved quantity. If one wishes energy to change without changing volume (b), then p must change. In other words, the Noether conserved quantity p could change without any symmetry breaking constraint being changed or $V(x)$ being applied. In particular, a particle could receive energy from a photon. We suggest that this accounts for the reason that (2) writes:

$dE = dN - \text{delta Work}$, where N is a Noether conserved quantity linked with no spatial symmetry breaking whereas Work is linked with symmetry breaking or a change in the parameter b in the Lagrangian in (2). In other words, we try to obtain the conclusions of (2) by considering a single particle and its interactions with both a moving wall and photons in terms of spatial symmetry-breaking and non-spatial symmetry breaking interactions.

References

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